

Hormonal contraceptive use and pharmacist counseling among women in Duhok, Iraq

Zana Sabri Qasim¹

1 College of Pharmacy, Nawroz University, Duhok, Kurdistan region of Iraq, Iraq

2 Department of Clinical Pharmacy, College of Pharmacy, Cihan University, Duhok, Kurdistan region of Iraq, Iraq

3 Sinjar General Hospital, Sinjar, Iraq

4 College of Pharmacy, University of Duhok, Duhok, Kurdistan region of Iraq, Iraq

Corresponding author: Darya Salih Hussein (darya.hussein@duhokcihan.edu.krd)

Received 5 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 2 June 2026 ♦ Published 11 June 2026

Citation: Sabri Qasim Z, Salih Hussein D, Khaleel Khalaf S, Firas Mahmood F, Abdulrahman Tegir Z, Khayri Husain S (2026) Hormonal contraceptive use and pharmacist counseling among women in Duhok, Iraq. *Pharmacia* 73: e190727. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e190727>

Abstract

Introduction: Hormonal contraceptives are widely used for pregnancy prevention; however, gaps in knowledge, attitudes, and practices may affect their safe and effective use. Pharmacists play a key role in counseling women regarding proper contraceptive use.

Aim: To assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice toward hormonal contraceptives and evaluate the role of pharmacists among women of reproductive age in Duhok, Iraq.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among women of reproductive age in Duhok. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing knowledge, usage patterns, and pharmacist counseling. Statistical analysis was performed to determine associations between contraceptive use and sociodemographic variables.

Results: Knowledge of hormonal contraceptives was moderate, with 51.7% identifying pregnancy prevention as the primary purpose. Awareness of specific methods was limited, particularly emergency contraception (1.5%), and only 20.9% recognized the correct timing for its use. Oral contraceptives were the most commonly used method (80.1%), mainly obtained from pharmacies (71.3%), with 40.4% reporting self-medication. Correct use of oral contraceptive pills was identified by 52.3% of participants. Pharmacist counseling was reported by 52.9%, primarily focusing on instructions for use, whereas counseling on side effects, missed doses, and drug interactions was limited. Side effects were reported by 12.8%, most commonly mood changes and gynecological disturbances. Significant associations were found between contraceptive use and age, marital status, education level, and urban residence.

Conclusion: There are notable gaps in knowledge and practice regarding hormonal contraceptives among women in Duhok. Strengthening pharmacist-led counseling, particularly regarding side effects, missed doses, and drug interactions, is essential to promote safe and effective contraceptive use.

Keywords

Duhok, emergency contraception, hormonal contraceptives, oral contraceptive pills, pharmacist counseling, self-medication

Introduction

Contraception is an essential component of medical practice aimed at preventing unintended pregnancies and promoting reproductive health (Daidone et al. 2024). It is a highly effective intervention, with more than 88% of women who wish to avoid pregnancy reporting the use of some form of contraception (Festin 2020). Ensuring access to safe and effective contraceptive methods is critical not only for women's health but also for broader societal well-being. Family planning reduces pregnancy-related health risks, lowers rates of abortion and infant mortality, and contributes to population stabilization (Jahanfar et al. 2020). In addition, certain contraceptive methods help reduce the transmission of sexually transmitted infections, including HIV (Salad et al. 2023). The utilization of contraceptives is influenced by multiple behavioral and sociodemographic factors, including age at marriage, educational level, partner communication, access to accurate information, financial status, and availability of healthcare services (Jahanfar et al. 2020). Over the past decades, family planning has been recognized as one of the most significant public health achievements. Globally, the contraceptive prevalence rate among women of reproductive age increased from 28% in 1970 to 48% in 2019, alongside a rise in demand satisfaction from 55% to 79% (Haakenstad et al. 2022). Furthermore, awareness of contraceptive methods has improved substantially, with only a small proportion of women in most countries remaining unaware of family planning options (Sedgh et al. 2016).

Despite these advancements, unintended pregnancies continue to pose significant public health challenges because of their association with unsafe abortions, maternal morbidity, and mortality (Fawcus 2008). In Iraq, unintended pregnancy remains a major concern. A cross-sectional study conducted in Erbil reported that 39.4% of pregnancies were unplanned, with higher proportions observed among women aged over 35 years and those with lower income levels (Salih and Zangana 2022). Similarly, a study among married women in Mosul found that 13.5% had attempted to induce abortion using medications, herbal preparations, or physical methods. Higher rates of induced abortion were observed among housewives, women with unemployed husbands, and those who did not use contraceptive methods (Al-Ridhwany et al. 2018). These findings highlight ongoing challenges in contraceptive utilization and reproductive health outcomes.

Promoting the use of contraceptives remains a vital public health measure to avoid unwanted births and the problems associated with them (Alomair 2022). Additional benefits of family planning include helping couples manage financial restrictions, space and plan pregnancies, and enhance the health of both mothers and children, all of which contribute to an overall improvement in quality of life (Alomair 2022). Hormonal contraceptives are efficient, although their actual effectiveness frequently deviates from ideal circumstances, primarily because of non-adherence and cessation (Burke et al. 2021).

Therefore, evaluating both user-related factors and healthcare support systems is essential.

Pharmacists, as highly accessible healthcare professionals, play a critical role in contraceptive counseling and service provision. Their responsibilities extend beyond dispensing medications to include patient education on method selection, correct use, management of missed doses, potential side effects, and drug–drug interactions. Pharmacists also contribute to improving adherence and addressing misconceptions, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and safety of contraceptive use (Fadhil et al. 2023; Daidone et al. 2024; Beshna et al. 2025). Pharmacists in some settings are authorized to prescribe or dispense hormonal contraceptives under specific protocols, improving access and continuity of use (Newlon et al. 2022; Whalen et al. 2024).

However, gaps remain in women's knowledge, correct use, and counseling quality, especially in low- and middle-income countries. This highlights the need to assess women's knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding hormonal contraceptives, as well as pharmacist counseling in local settings such as Duhok, Iraq. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) toward hormonal contraceptives among women of reproductive age in Duhok and to assess the role of pharmacists in counseling. It also explores factors influencing contraceptive choice, usage patterns, and awareness of safety issues, including side effects, drug interactions, and the importance of professional advice.

Materials and methods

Study design

The knowledge, attitudes, and practices of women of reproductive age regarding the use of contraceptives were evaluated, as well as the role that pharmacists play in offering contraceptive counseling and guidance, using a descriptive cross-sectional study. This design is suitable for providing a brief overview of the target population's current awareness, behavior, and perceptions.

Study setting and duration

The study was conducted in Duhok City, in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, at several healthcare facilities and community pharmacies. Over the course of 3 months, from December 2025 to February 2026, data were gathered.

Study population

Participants were recruited using a convenience sampling approach. Eligible women were approached in person at participating community pharmacies and healthcare facilities by trained pharmacists, who explained the study and invited them to participate. Women who agreed were provided with the questionnaire either in paper form, face-to-face, or via an electronic link. The questionnaire

was prepared in Kurdish, Arabic, and English. Responses obtained in Kurdish and Arabic were translated into English prior to data analysis to ensure consistency. Data collection was conducted using both face-to-face and electronic formats. The electronic questionnaire was created using an online survey platform and distributed via QR codes displayed at participating pharmacies, as well as shared directly with eligible participants. Participants were able to complete the questionnaire on their personal devices at their convenience. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to participation after a clear explanation of the study's aim and purpose.

Sampling method and sample size

A convenience sampling technique was employed to select participants who met the inclusion criteria. The required sample size was determined using the single-proportion formula for cross-sectional studies:

$$n_0 = (Z^2 \times p \times (1 - p)) / d^2,$$

where Z represents the standard normal value corresponding to a 95% confidence level (1.96), p is the estimated prevalence of contraceptive use, and d is the margin of error (0.05). Based on a previously reported prevalence of contraceptive use in Duhok ($p = 0.606$), the calculated minimum sample size (n_0) is 367 participants.

Due to the limited number of eligible women available during the study period, 327 women who met the inclusion criteria were ultimately enrolled. Although this number was slightly lower than the calculated target, the achieved sample still provided acceptable statistical precision, corresponding to an approximate margin of error of 5.4% at the 95% confidence level, which remains close to the planned precision level. Furthermore, similar cross-sectional studies assessing contraceptive knowledge, attitudes, and practices have reported reliable findings using comparable sample sizes.

To reduce potential bias, standardized procedures were applied at all pharmacies, and questionnaires were checked upon collection for completeness and consistency. Missing critical data (e.g., contraceptive use status, age, and marital status) resulted in exclusion from the analysis, whereas non-critical missing data (e.g., individual knowledge or attitude items) were handled using pairwise deletion to maximize the use of available data.

Data collection tool

Following a thorough analysis of pertinent literature, the researchers created a structured, self-administered questionnaire to gather data. The questionnaire was assessed for validity prior to data collection. Content validity was evaluated by a panel of experts in pharmacy practice and public health, who reviewed the questionnaire for relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. Face validity was assessed by a small group of participants from the

target population to ensure clarity and appropriateness of the questions. Minor modifications were made based on feedback. Additionally, the questionnaire was reviewed to ensure readability and ease of understanding. The questionnaire was distributed both face-to-face and online to eligible participants. The survey was divided into four primary sections:

1. Demographic data, including age, marital status, education, occupation, and place of residence.
2. Understanding of contraceptives, including their types, applications, adverse effects, emergency contraception, and prescription needs.
3. Use and practice patterns: types of contraceptives used, access points, length of use, adverse effects, and self-medication habits.
4. Pharmacist role and safety awareness: perceptions of pharmacists' participation in contraceptive education, counseling experience, and comfort level with pharmacist engagement.

Ethical considerations

Participation in this study was voluntary. Women of reproductive age attending six community pharmacies in Duhok, Iraq, were informed about the study's purpose and objectives prior to participation. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants before completing the questionnaire. To ensure privacy and confidentiality, no directly identifiable information, such as names or addresses, was collected, and all responses were recorded anonymously and used solely for research purposes. The research proposal was reviewed, evaluated, and approved by the Scientific and Ethics Committee of the College of Pharmacy, Nawroz University, in accordance with applicable scientific and ethical standards (Reference No. 0133, 18 October 2025). A structured questionnaire and standardized data collection procedures were applied across all pharmacies to minimize bias. Questionnaires were checked at the point of collection to reduce missing data, and incomplete responses were appropriately managed during statistical analysis.

Pilot testing

To ensure validity, reliability, and clarity, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 10% of the total sample prior to the main study. Feedback obtained from the pilot study was used to make necessary modifications and improvements, ensuring that the final version of the questionnaire was clear and comprehensive for participants. In addition, content validity was assessed by a panel of experts in pharmacy practice and public health, who reviewed the questionnaire for relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. Face validity was also confirmed during the pilot testing process. The questionnaire was translated into Kurdish and Arabic and back-translated into English to ensure linguistic accuracy and consistency.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics software (version 25.0). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant characteristics, including frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was applied to assess associations between categorical variables. Binary logistic regression analysis was performed to estimate crude odds ratios (CORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for factors associated with contraceptive use. A *p*-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Sociodemographic and reproductive characteristics of participants

A total of 327 women of reproductive age participated in the study. Regarding marital status, 174 (51.2%) participants were married, while 153 (46.8%) were single.

In terms of age distribution, most participants were aged 25–29 years, 130 (39.8%), followed by those aged 19–24 years, 89 (27.2%), and 30–34 years, 65 (19.9%). Participants aged 35–39 years accounted for 27 (8.3%), while 16 (4.9%) were aged 40 years and above.

Regarding educational level, most participants had a university education, 131 (40.1%), followed by those with a diploma, 90 (27.5%). Participants with secondary education constituted 42 (12.8%), postgraduate education 36 (11.0%), and primary education 28 (8.6%).

With respect to occupation, 100 (30.6%) participants were employed, while 80 (24.5%) were unemployed and an equal number, 80 (24.5%), were housewives. Students represented 67 (20.5%) of the study population. The majority of participants, 215 (65.5%), resided in urban areas, whereas 112 (34.3%) lived in rural areas.

In terms of economic status, most participants reported a middle economic status, 237 (72.5%). A smaller proportion reported a low economic status, 28 (8.6%), or high economic status, 19 (5.8%), while 43 (13.1%) preferred not to disclose their economic status, as shown in Table 1.

Association between sociodemographic characteristics and contraceptive use

Chi-square analysis showed significant associations between contraceptive use and several sociodemographic characteristics, including age group, marital status, residence, education level, and occupation. Age group was significantly associated with contraceptive use ($p < 0.001$). Binary logistic regression analysis indicated that, compared with women aged 19–24 years (reference group), women aged 25–29 years were more likely to use contraceptives (COR = 3.61, 95% CI: 1.85–7.03). The likelihood of contraceptive use increased further among women aged 30–34 years (COR = 5.92, 95% CI: 2.78–12.61) and 35–39 years (COR = 12.05, 95% CI: 4.48–32.39). Women aged 40

Table 1. Sociodemographic and reproductive characteristics of participants ($n = 327$).

Marital status	Frequency (%)
Married	174 (51.2)
Single	153 (46.8)
Age group	
19–24	89 (27.2)
25–29	130 (39.8)
30–34	65 (19.9)
35–39	27 (8.3)
40 and higher	16 (4.9)
Education	
Diploma	90 (27.5)
Postgraduate	36 (11.0)
Primary	28 (8.6)
Secondary	42 (12.8)
University	131 (40.1)
Occupation	
Employed	100 (30.6)
Unemployed	80 (24.5)
Student	67 (20.5)
Housewife	80 (24.5)
Residence	
Rural	112 (34.3)
Urban	215 (65.5)
Economic status	
High	19 (5.8)
Low	28 (8.6)
Middle	237 (72.5)
Prefer not to say	43 (13.1)
Number of abortions	
0	131 (75.3)
1	34 (19.5)
2	9 (5.2)
Number of children	
Have children	111 (33.9)
Do not have children	216 (66.1)

years and above had the highest odds of contraceptive use (COR = 35.50, 95% CI: 7.13–176.71).

Marital status was also significantly associated with contraceptive use ($p < 0.001$). Married women were substantially more likely to use contraceptives compared with single women (COR = 19.05, 95% CI: 10.34–35.08).

Residence showed a significant association with contraceptive use ($p = 0.002$). Participants living in urban areas were approximately twice as likely to use contraceptives compared with those living in rural areas (COR = 2.07, 95% CI: 1.29–3.33).

Education level was significantly associated with contraceptive use ($p < 0.001$). Compared with participants with university education (reference group), those with primary education had higher odds of contraceptive use (COR = 4.47, 95% CI: 1.82–10.98), followed by those with secondary education (COR = 2.83, 95% CI: 1.36–5.89). However, diploma (COR = 1.35, 95% CI: 0.76–2.39) and postgraduate education (COR = 1.69, 95% CI: 0.79–3.63) were not statistically significant.

Table 2. Association between sociodemographic characteristics and contraceptive use ($n = 327$).

Variable	Used no. (%)	Did not use no. (%)	P-value	COR	95% CI
Age group					
19–24	14 (16.5%)	75 (83.5%)	< 0.001	1.00	Reference
25–29	54 (41.5%)	76 (58.5%)		3.61	1.85–7.03
30–34	35 (53.8%)	30 (46.2%)		5.92	2.78–12.61
35–39	19 (70.4%)	8 (29.6%)		12.05	4.48–32.39
40 and higher	14 (87.5%)	2 (12.5%)		35.50	7.13–176.71
Marital status					
Single	16 (10.5%)	137 (89.5%)	< 0.001	1.00	Reference
Married	120 (69.0%)	54 (31.0%)		19.05	10.34–35.08
Residence					
Rural	34 (30.4%)	78 (69.6%)	0.002	1.00	Reference
Urban	102 (47.4%)	113 (52.6%)		2.07	1.29–3.33
Education level					
University	42 (32.1%)	89 (67.9%)	< 0.001	1.00	Reference
Diploma	35 (38.9%)	55 (61.1%)		1.35	0.76–2.39
Postgraduate	16 (44.4%)	20 (55.6%)		1.69	0.79–3.63
Primary	19 (67.9%)	9 (32.1%)		4.47	1.82–10.98
Secondary	24 (57.1%)	18 (42.9%)		2.83	1.36–5.89
Occupation					
Student	11 (16.4%)	56 (83.6%)	< 0.001	1.00	Reference
Employed	44 (44.0%)	56 (56.0%)		4.00	1.85–8.63
Housewife	51 (63.7%)	29 (36.3%)		8.97	4.01–20.05
Unemployed	30 (37.5%)	50 (62.5%)		3.06	1.39–6.71

Occupation was also significantly associated with contraceptive use ($p < 0.001$). Compared with students (reference group), employed participants had higher odds of contraceptive use (COR = 4.00, 95% CI: 1.85–8.63). Housewives were more likely to use contraceptives (COR = 8.97, 95% CI: 4.01–20.05), and unemployed participants also showed higher odds (COR = 3.06, 95% CI: 1.39–6.71), as shown in Table 2.

Knowledge regarding hormonal contraceptives

Table 3 presents the participants' varying levels of knowledge regarding hormonal contraceptives. More than half of the participants identified pregnancy prevention as the main purpose of contraceptive use, 169 (51.7%), while 64 (19.5%) recognized multiple purposes. However, 61 (18.7%) reported that they did not know the main purpose of contraceptive use.

Regarding knowledge of contraceptive types, over half of the participants were able to identify multiple types of contraceptives, 182 (55.6%). Oral contraceptive pills were identified by 57 (17.4%) participants, followed by male condoms, 19 (5.8%), and intrauterine devices (IUDs), 17 (5.2%). Knowledge of injections, eight (2.5%), and emergency contraceptive pills, five (1.5%), was comparatively low.

In terms of knowledge of correct use, 171 (52.3%) correctly reported that oral contraceptive pills are taken daily. Nevertheless, a substantial proportion of participants demonstrated inadequate knowledge, with 138 (42.2%)

indicating that they did not know how oral contraceptive pills are usually taken.

Knowledge regarding emergency contraception was limited. Only 68 (20.9%) participants correctly identified

Table 3. Knowledge regarding hormonal contraceptives ($n = 327$).

Knowledge of the purpose of contraceptive use	Frequency (%)
Prevent pregnancy	169 (51.7)
Regulate menstruation	30 (9.2)
Treat acne	3 (0.9)
Multiple purpose	64 (19.5)
Do not know	61 (18.7)
Knowledge of types of contraceptives	
Oral pills	57 (17.4)
Intrauterine device (IUD)	17 (5.2)
Injections	8 (2.45)
Male condoms	19 (5.8)
Emergency pill	5 (1.5)
Withdrawal method	39 (11.9)
Multiple types	182 (55.6)
Knowledge of correct use	
Daily	171 (52.3)
Weekly	4 (1.2)
Only during menstruation	14 (4.3)
Do not know	138 (42.2)
Knowledge of emergency contraception	
Within 24 hours	68 (20.9)
Within 72 hours	63 (19.2)
After 1 week	3 (0.9)
Do not know	193 (59.0)

that emergency contraceptives should be taken within 24 hours of unprotected intercourse, while 63 (19.2%) reported within 72 hours. The majority of participants, 193 (59.0%), indicated that they did not know the correct timing for emergency contraceptive use.

Practice and use patterns among users

Of the total 327 participants, 136 (41.6%) reported using hormonal contraceptives and were therefore included in the analysis of practice and utilization patterns, as presented in Table 4. The most commonly used hormonal contraceptive method was oral contraceptive pills, reported by 109 (80.1%) women. This was followed by IUDs, used by 12 (8.8%) participants. Injectable contraceptives were reported by six (4.4%) women, implants by four (2.9%), and five (3.7%) participants reported using multiple types of hormonal contraceptives.

Table 4. Practice and use patterns among users ($n = 136$).

Type of hormonal contraceptive used	Frequency (%)
Pills	109 (80.1)
Injections	6 (4.4)
IUD	12 (8.8)
Implant	4 (2.9)
Multiple types	5 (3.7)
Source of recommendation	
Doctor	90 (66.2)
Pharmacist	7 (5.1)
Self	11 (8.1)
Relative/friend	13 (9.6)
Others	15 (11.0)
Duration of hormonal contraceptive use	
< 6 Months	76 (55.9)
6–12 Months	18 (13.2)
1–3 Years	15 (11.0)
> 3 Years	27 (19.9)
Usual source of obtaining	
Pharmacy	97 (71.3)
Private clinic	10 (7.4)
Health center	5 (3.7)
Others	24 (17.6)
Main reason for self-medication	
Advice from friends	29 (22.0)
Easy availability	33 (25.0)
Previous experience	58 (43.9)
Shyness to consult doctor	12 (9.1)

Regarding the source of recommendation, the majority of participants, 90 (66.2%), reported that contraceptives were recommended by physicians. Recommendations from relatives or friends accounted for 13 (9.6%), while 11 (8.1%) initiated use on their own. Pharmacists were the source of recommendation for seven (5.1%) participants, and 15 (11.0%) reported other sources.

In terms of duration of use, more than half of the women, 76 (55.9%), had been using hormonal contraceptives

for less than 6 months. Meanwhile, 18 (13.2%) reported use for 6–12 months, 15 (11.0%) for 1–3 years, and 27 (19.9%) for more than 3 years.

Concerning the usual source of obtaining hormonal contraceptives, pharmacies were the most common source, reported by 97 (71.3%) participants. This was followed by other sources, 24 (17.6%), private clinics, 10 (7.4%), and health centers, five (3.7%).

Regarding safety practices, 132 (97.1%) participants reported using hormonal contraceptives without prior medical advice. The main reasons for this practice included convenience and easy access to pharmacies, prior experience with the method, the perception that medical consultation was unnecessary, and time constraints. Overall, the findings indicate that oral contraceptive pills are the predominant method used, physicians are the primary source of recommendation, and pharmacies serve as the main point of access for hormonal contraceptives among women of reproductive age in Duhok, Iraq.

Pharmacist role and safety awareness

The findings related to pharmacist counseling and safety awareness are described narratively to provide detailed insights, while summary indicators are presented in Table 5. Among the contraceptive users ($n = 136$), 86 (63.2%) reported receiving instructions on how to use the medication. Information about side effects was provided to 16 (11.8%), while eight (5.9%) were counseled about missed doses and five (3.7%) about drug interactions. Additionally, 21 (15.4%) received multiple types of information. However, 14 (10.3%) stated that they did not receive any counseling from the pharmacist. These findings indicate that while pharmacists commonly provide basic instructions on use, counseling regarding safety-related aspects such as side effects, missed doses, and drug interactions remains comparatively limited.

Table 5 summarizes participants' knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding hormonal contraceptives and the role of pharmacists ($n = 327$). Among hormonal contraceptive users ($n = 136$), 132 (97.1%) reported using hormonal contraceptives without prior medical advice, indicating a high prevalence of self-medication within this subgroup. When calculated based on the total study population, self-medication was reported by 132 (40.4%) participants.

Additionally, 173 (52.9%) stated that they had received counseling from a pharmacist about contraceptive use. In terms of knowledge, 264 (80.7%) were aware that contraceptives can cause side effects, and 286 (87.5%) knew that some contraceptives require a doctor's prescription. Furthermore, 219 (67.0%) were aware of potential drug interactions, and 231 (70.6%) knew that pharmacists can provide advice and guidance on contraceptives, while 60 (18.3%) were unsure.

Regarding attitude, 255 (78.0%) supported a greater role for pharmacists in contraceptive education, and 206 (63.0%) reported feeling comfortable asking pharmacists about contraception. However, only 104 (31.8%) considered the over-the-counter sale of contraceptives

Table 5. Knowledge, attitude, and practice toward hormonal contraceptives and the role of pharmacists ($n = 327$).

Question	Frequency (%)	
	Yes	No
Practice		
1. Have you ever used any contraceptive method?	136 (41.6)	191 (58.4)
2. Have you ever used any hormonal contraceptive?	136 (41.6)	191 (58.4)
3. Have you ever used contraceptives without medical advice (self-medication)?	132 (40.4)	195 (59.6)
4. Have you ever received counseling from a pharmacist about contraceptive use?	173 (52.9)	154 (46.1)
Knowledge		
5. Do you know that contraceptives can have side effects?	264 (80.7)	63 (19.3)
6. Do you know any emergency contraceptive method?	113 (34.6)	214 (65.4)
7. Do you know that some contraceptives require a doctor's prescription?	286 (87.5)	41 (12.5)
8. Are you aware that contraceptives may interact with other medicines?	219 (67.0)	108 (33.0)
Attitude		
9. Do you think pharmacists should have a bigger role in contraceptive education?	255 (78.0)	72 (22.0)
10. Would you feel comfortable asking a pharmacist about contraception?	206 (63.0)	121 (37.0)
11. Do you think over-the-counter sale of contraceptives without a prescription is appropriate?	104 (31.8)	223 (68.2)

without a prescription to be appropriate. Concerning awareness of the pharmacist's role in contraceptive counseling, 231 (70.6%) reported that pharmacists can provide advice and guidance, 36 (11.0%) responded negatively, and 60 (18.3%) indicated that they were unsure.

Discussion

Understanding women's sociodemographic characteristics is essential for interpreting contraceptive knowledge and utilization, as factors such as age, education, marital status, and residence influence reproductive health behaviors (Sharma et al. 2012). In this study, most participants were aged 25–29 years, with nearly equal marital distribution, high university education, and predominance of urban residence. Contraceptive use was significantly associated with age, marital status, education, and residence, with higher uptake among older, married, educated, and urban women.

Comparable patterns have been documented in Iraq and the broader region, where studies from Mosul and Erbil reported higher contraceptive knowledge and use among married, urban, and more educated women (Ismail et al. 2014; Aldabbagh and Al-Qazaz 2020).

Similarly, studies from Saudi Arabia, including Al-Qunfudah and Makkah, identified urban residence, older age, and marital status as key predictors of contraceptive knowledge and practice, highlighting the influence of sociodemographic and access-related factors on women's reproductive health behavior (Alkalash et al. 2023; Alsharif et al. 2023). Taken together, these observations suggest that although demographic and educational factors consistently shape contraceptive behavior, their effects vary locally, highlighting persistent gaps among younger, unmarried, less educated, and rural women.

Equitable access to contraceptive services is essential for enabling women to achieve their reproductive goals and can significantly reduce rates of unplanned pregnancies and abortions (Wang and Cao 2019). However, a lack of aware-

ness about the availability and benefits of these services may limit their impact. In the present study, knowledge of hormonal contraceptives among women in Duhok was moderate, with substantial gaps in critical areas. Approximately half of the participants correctly identified the purpose of contraceptives, but overall knowledge gaps remained, particularly regarding specific use and emergency contraception (Abdelaziz et al. 2023; Alkalash et al. 2023). Knowledge of contraceptive types was variable; most participants could identify multiple methods, yet recognition of specific options, such as emergency contraceptive pills, was extremely low, a trend similarly reported in Mosul and Lebanon (Al-dabbagh and Al-Qazaz 2020; Samaha et al. 2025). Correct use of oral contraceptives was understood by just over half of the women, and awareness of the appropriate timing for emergency contraception was particularly limited, with the majority unaware that it should be taken within 24 hours. These findings suggest adequate general awareness but poor detailed knowledge (Alameer et al. 2022; Samaha et al. 2025).

In terms of practice, oral contraceptive pills were the most commonly used method in this study, while long-acting methods were less frequently used. This pattern mirrors findings from Iraq and neighboring countries, where short-acting reversible methods such as pills are consistently the most common choice. For example, research in Mosul, Iraq, similarly reported a high reliance on oral contraceptives, with long-acting methods less frequently adopted outside clinical settings, reflecting user preferences and accessibility considerations (Aldabbagh and Al-Qazaz 2020). Comparable trends have also been documented in Saudi Arabia, where women preferentially use oral pills over IUDs or injectables, particularly in urban and university-educated populations (Alkalash et al. 2023; Alsharif et al. 2023).

Awareness of emergency contraception was very low, likely because of limited education and cultural factors. Similar disparities have been reported in low- and middle-income settings, where emergency contraception is either poorly promoted or inconsistently discussed during pharmacy encounters (Dawson et al. 2015). Nona et al. demonstrated

that pharmacists' knowledge and guidance regarding emergency contraception are frequently limited, emphasizing the need for structured training programs to enhance competence and confidence in patient counseling (Nona et al. 2025).

Despite the generally good tolerability of hormonal contraceptives, with only 12.8% reporting side effects, counseling remains essential. Mood changes, menstrual disturbances, and gastrointestinal symptoms were the most commonly reported adverse effects, consistent with regional and international evidence (Nappi et al. 2015; Salh and Abdulridha 2025).

The observed rate of contraceptive self-medication (40.4%) is clinically and ethically significant. This finding should be interpreted within the regulatory context of Iraq, where hormonal contraceptives are widely accessible through community pharmacies without strict prescription control. While improving access, it raises concerns about inappropriate and unsupervised use.

Unsupervised use increases the risks of contraindications and drug interactions. These risks highlight the ethical responsibility of pharmacists to ensure safe medication use through appropriate screening and patient counseling. Despite physicians remaining the primary source of contraceptive recommendations, the substantial role of pharmacies in direct access and self-medication underscores the need for stronger integration of pharmacists into formal contraceptive care pathways. International evidence supports these concerns. In Kuwait, a significant proportion of women initiated oral contraceptives without medical consultation (Shah et al. 2001), while data from the United States indicate that over-the-counter access increases initiation but may bypass essential counseling, particularly among first-time users (Rodriguez et al. 2025). These findings suggest that increased accessibility must be accompanied by structured pharmacist involvement to ensure safe use.

Pharmacist counseling gaps in Duhok are consistent with regional findings (Ibrahim and Hussein 2017; Hamasalih and Nitham 2021; Chahine and Souheil 2022). These systemic gaps in patient education likely contribute to the moderate awareness and adherence challenges observed among women in the Middle East (Salh and Abdulridha 2025). These gaps likely contribute to moderate awareness and suboptimal use.

Evidence from systematic and interventional studies indicates that pharmacist-led contraceptive services can significantly improve access, continuity of use, and patient satisfaction. Structured pharmacy-based programs and pharmacist prescribing models have been associated with improved uptake and reduced unintended pregnancies. Furthermore, expanded pharmacist authority has been shown to enhance timely initiation of contraception and improve service

accessibility, particularly in community-based settings where pharmacies often serve as the first point of contact (Rodriguez et al. 2020; Buckingham et al. 2021; Eckhaus et al. 2021).

Pharmacies therefore represent a critical yet underutilized component of reproductive healthcare systems. Their accessibility, extended working hours, and no requirement for appointments reduce barriers to contraceptive initiation and continuation. However, maximizing their impact requires moving beyond dispensing toward fully integrated pharmaceutical care models supported by structured protocols and regulatory frameworks.

Collectively, these findings highlight the need to strengthen pharmacist involvement in contraceptive care through training and structured counseling. This is particularly relevant in settings such as Duhok, where self-medication is common and pharmacist counseling is limited. Integrating pharmacists more effectively into family planning services may improve patient education, reduce unsupervised contraceptive use, and enhance reproductive health outcomes. While these findings have important implications, several limitations should be considered. The cross-sectional design limits causal inference. Self-reported data may introduce recall and social desirability bias. In addition, the single-center setting in Duhok limits generalizability to other populations.

Conclusion

Understanding public awareness and knowledge gaps regarding hormonal contraceptives is essential for improving reproductive health outcomes and ensuring their safe and effective use. This study demonstrates that women of reproductive age in Duhok have moderate overall knowledge of hormonal contraceptives, with significant gaps in awareness of emergency contraception and correct use. Oral contraceptives were the predominant method, often obtained directly from pharmacies, and self-medication was common, reflecting limited engagement with professional guidance.

While pharmacists provided basic instructions on use, counseling on important safety aspects, such as side effects, management of missed doses, and potential drug interactions, remained insufficient. Side effects were reported by a proportion of users, most commonly mood changes, gynecological disturbances, and gastrointestinal symptoms. Contraceptive use was significantly influenced by sociodemographic factors, including age, marital status, education level, and urban residence. These findings underscore the need for targeted educational interventions and strengthened pharmacist-led counseling to promote safe, informed, and effective contraceptive practices in this population.

References

- Abdelaziz W, Nofal Z, Al-Neyazy S (2023) Factors affecting contraceptive use among currently married women in Iraq in 2018. *Journal of Biosocial Science* 55: 449–462. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932022000104>
- Alameer MI, Muqri KY, Awlaqi AA, Azyabi FY, Yaqoub AM, Suhail HM, Shabaan S, Moafa MH, Alhazmi MA, Alhazmi A (2022) Knowledge, attitude and practices regarding contraceptive pill and its side effects

- among women in Jazan Region, Saudi Arabia. *Clinics and Practice* 12: 268–275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/clinpract12030032>
- Aldabbagh RO, Al-Qazaz HK (2020) Knowledge and practice of contraception use among females of child-bearing age in Mosul, Iraq. *International Journal of Women's Health* 12: 107. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJWH.S231529>
- Alkalash SH, Alessi SM, Alrizqi AA, Alamri AA, Al Kenani A, Alrizqi HA, Alqozi R (2023) Knowledge on, attitude toward, and practice of contraceptive methods among females of reproductive age in Al-Qunfudah Governorate, Saudi Arabia. *Cureus* 15(3): e36606. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.36606>
- Alomair N (2022) Sexual and reproductive health of women in Saudi Arabia: Needs, perceptions, and experiences. PhD Thesis, University College London, London, UK. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10146351/>
- Al-Ridhwany H, Aljawadi A, Abduljawad M (2018) Use of induced abortion for birth control by mothers in Iraq. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal* 24: 644–652. <https://doi.org/10.26719/2018.24.7.644>
- Alsharif SS, Saeed RIA, Alskhairi RF, Almuwallad SA, Mandili FA, Shatla M (2023) Knowledge, attitude, and practice of contraception use among childbearing women in Makkah Region, Saudi Arabia. *Cureus* 15: e34848. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.34848>
- Beshna EA, Said WA, Meera WA, Salman GA, Alkeelani A, Altumi SA (2025) Knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding dietary supplements: Community pharmacies-based cross-sectional study in Yefren, Libya. *Al Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 24: 443–450. <https://doi.org/10.32947/ajps.v24i4.1193>
- Buckingham P, Amos N, Hussaini SY, Mazza D (2021) Pharmacy-based initiatives to reduce unintended pregnancies: A scoping review. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 17: 1673–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2021.01.016>
- Burke KL, Thaxton L, Potter JE (2021) Short-acting hormonal contraceptive continuation among low-income postpartum women in Texas. *Contraception* X 3: 100052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conx.2020.100052>
- Chahine B, Al Souheil F (2022) Oral contraceptives: knowledge and counselling practices of Lebanese community pharmacists. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 30: 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpp/riab069>
- Daidone C, Morris K, Colquitt J, Jackson G (2024) Provider perspectives on analgesic use in intrauterine device insertion procedures: A mixed methods analysis. *Cureus* 16: e56580. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.56580>
- Dawson A, Tran NT, Westley E, Mangiaterra V, Festin M (2015) Workforce interventions to improve access to emergency contraception pills: a systematic review of current evidence in low- and middle-income countries and recommendations for improving performance. *BMC Health Services Research* 15: 180. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-015-0815-2>
- Eckhaus LM, Ti AJ, Curtis KM, Stewart-Lynch AL, Whiteman MK (2021) Patient and pharmacist perspectives on pharmacist-prescribed contraception: A systematic review. *Contraception* 103: 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2020.10.012>
- Fadhil EB, Mohammed MM, Alkawaz UM (2023) Influence of letrozole and Co Q10 on sex hormones and spermogram in infertile men; sample of Iraqi patients. *Al Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 23: 345–354. <https://doi.org/10.32947/ajps.v23i3.1053>
- Fawcus SR (2008) Maternal mortality and unsafe abortion. *Best Practice and Research: Clinical Obstetrics and Gynaecology* 22: 533–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2007.10.006>
- Festin MPR (2020) Overview of modern contraception. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology* 66: 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2020.03.004>
- Haakenstad A, Angelino O, Irvine CMS, Bhutta ZA, Bienhoff K, Bintz C, Causey K, Dirac MA, Fullman N, Gakidou E, Glucksmann T, Hay SI, Henry NJ, Martopullo I, Mokdad AH, Mumford JE, Lim SS, Murray CJL, Lozano R (2022) Measuring contraceptive method mix, prevalence, and demand satisfied by age and marital status in 204 countries and territories, 1970–2019: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet* 400: 295–327. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(22\)00936-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(22)00936-9)
- Hamasalih K, Nitham W (2021) Nature and extent of counseling practice in community pharmacies in Sulaimani city, Iraq: A cross-sectional study. *Zanco Journal of Medical Sciences* 25: 686–691. <https://doi.org/10.15218/zjms.2021.035>
- Ibrahim OM, Hussein RN (2017) Knowledge of pharmacists on proper use of oral contraceptive pills and missed dose instructions in United Arab Emirates. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 16: 947. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v16i4.29>
- Ismail Z, Al-Tawil N, Hasan S (2014) Knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding family planning among two groups of women in Erbil. *Zanco Journal of Medical Sciences* 18: 710–717. <https://doi.org/10.15218/zjms.2014.0022>
- Jahanfar M, Hamzehgardeshi S, Fooladi Z (2020) An investigation into long-acting reversible contraception: Use, awareness, and associated factors. *European Journal of Environment and Public Health* 2020: 39. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejeph/7837>
- Nappi RE, Pellegrinelli A, Campolo F, Lanzo G, Santamaria V, Suragna A, Spinillo A, Benedetto C (2015) Effects of combined hormonal contraception on health and wellbeing: women's knowledge in northern Italy. *European Journal of Contraception and Reproductive Health Care* 20: 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.3109/13625187.2014.961598>
- Newlon JL, Reed JB, Stone RH, Satterfield KG, Meredith AH (2022) Pharmacist-prescribed hormonal contraception services: A systematic review of implementation studies. *JACCP Journal of the American College of Clinical Pharmacy* 5: 85–98. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jac5.1539>
- Nona RA, Ray RA, Taylor SM, Glass BD (2025) Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of community pharmacists providing over-the-counter emergency hormonal contraception: a scoping review. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 33: 6–18. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpp/riae062>
- Rodriguez MI, Edelman AB, Skye M, Anderson L, Darney BG (2020) Association of pharmacist prescription with dispensed duration of hormonal contraception. *JAMA Network Open* 3: e205252–e205252. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.5252>
- Rodriguez MI, Burns H, Sheridan R, Edelman AB (2025) Over-the-counter oral contraceptive use and initiation of contraception. *JAMA Network Open* 8: e2527438–e2527438. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.27438>
- Salad AM, Duale HA, Gele A, Farah AA (2023) Hospital-based cross-sectional study on demographic aspects of hormonal contraception use and its association with depression among Somali women in Mogadishu. *East African Journal of Health and Science* 6: 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajhs.6.1.1167>
- Salh FM, Abdulridha MK (2025) Assessment of awareness about contraception among a sample of Iraqi women using hormonal contraceptives: a cross-sectional study. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e140451>

- Salih RK, Zangana J (2022) A cross sectional study about unintended pregnancy among women in Erbil, Kurdistan region of Iraq. *Journal of Medicinal and Chemical Sciences* 5: 171–176. <https://doi.org/10.26655/JMCHEMSCI.2022.2.4>
- Samaha H, Abou-Abbas L, Barakat Z, Lahoud N (2025) Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of Lebanese women toward the use of oral contraceptive pills. *BMC Women's Health* 25: 96. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-025-03618-1>
- Sedgh G, Ashford LS, Hussain R (2016) Unmet need for contraception in developing countries: Examining women's reasons for not using a method. Guttmacher Institute, New York. <https://www.guttmacher.org/report/unmet-need-for-contraception-in-developing-countries>
- Shah MA, Shah NM, Al-Rahmani E, Behbehani J, Radovanovic Z (2001) Over-the-counter use of oral contraceptives in Kuwait. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics* 73: 243–251. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7292\(01\)00375-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7292(01)00375-7)
- Sharma V, Mohan U, Das V, Awasthi S (2012) Socio demographic determinants and knowledge, attitude, practice: survey of family planning. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care* 1: 43. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.94451>
- Wang C, Cao H (2019) Persisting regional disparities in modern contraceptive use and unmet need for contraception among Nigerian Women. *BioMed Research International* 2019: 9103928. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9103928>
- Whalen A, Bratberg J, Cohen L, Orr K, Lemay V (2024) Assessing pharmacist and clinician perspectives on pharmacist-prescribed hormonal contraceptives. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 64: 314–320.e3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2023.11.013>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants before completing the questionnaire. To ensure privacy and confidentiality, no directly identifiable information, such as names or addresses, was collected, and all responses were recorded anonymously and used solely for research purposes. The research proposal was reviewed, evaluated, and approved by the Scientific and Ethics Committee of the College of Pharmacy, Nawroz University, in accordance with applicable scientific and ethical standards (Reference No. 0133, 18 October 2025).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Z.S.Q.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data collection, Formal analysis, Questionnaire Preparation, Writing. D.S.H.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data collection, Formal analysis, Writing. S.Kh.Kh.: Data collection, Writing. F.F.M.: Data collection, Questionnaire Preparation, Writing. Z.A.T.: Data collection, Writing. S.Kh.H.: Data collection, Writing.

Author ORCIDs

Z. Sabri Qasim <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-6347-4774>

D. Salih Hussein <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2046-1221>

S. Khaleel Khalaf <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9082-7071>

F. Firas Mahmood <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9064-9462>

Z. Abdulrahman Tegir <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1824-5258>

S. Khayri Husain <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8035-1778>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Questionnaire in English

Authors: Zana Sabri Qasim, Darya Salih Hussein, Slaviya Khaleel Khalaf, Fatima Firas Mahmood, Zaytoun Abdulrahman Tegir, Sozan Khayri Husain

Data type: pdf

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e190727.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Questionnaire in Kurdish

Authors: Zana Sabri Qasim, Darya Salih Hussein, Slaviya Khaleel Khalaf, Fatima Firas Mahmood, Zaytoun Abdulrahman Tegir, Sozan Khayri Husain

Data type: pdf

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e190727.suppl2>